

STUDY ON THE HIGH ORDER AERO-DAMPING OF A 1.5-STAGE COMPRESSOR ROTOR
IN STAGE ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Aerodynamic damping is a critical parameter in blade vibration analysis, particularly with the growing adoption of integrated bladed disks (blistks), the aero-damping prediction plays a significant role in the flutter stability analysis. In forced vibration scenarios, the level of aero-damping also strongly influences vibration amplitude. Compared with aero-damping of low order modes excitation, the impact of upstream and downstream blade rows on the aerodynamic damping of higher-order modes with complex shapes remains poorly understood, necessitating further investigation in a multi-stage context. This paper presents a numerical study of an axial compressor using full-annulus Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) simulations to evaluate the changes in aerodynamic damping due to the interactions with adjacent blade rows. A fluid-structure decoupling approach is employed to reduce the computational cost. The unsteady pressure sources are examined, and acoustic waves induced by blade vibration are radially decomposed to study the propagation behavior of different radial modes. Results show that under the various stage environments, the modal force amplitude during resonance slightly changes, while the aerodynamic damping varies considerably due to phase shifts induced by adjacent blade rows. The downstream stator significantly alters the pressure distribution on the rotor blade surface, whereas the upstream inlet guide vanes (IGVs) have negligible influence due to the behavior of reflected waves. Additionally, the amplitude of various radial acoustic modes is found to closely correlate with the blade mode shape.

Keywords: Forced Response, Aero-damping, Unsteady Aerodynamics, CFD

NOMENCLATURE

a	Speed of sound
m	Circumferential mode index
n	Radial mode index
k	Freestream acoustic wave number
k_z	Axial wave number
$k_{m,n}$	Eigenvalue of acoustic wave equation of mode(m,n)
$a_{m,n}$	Amplitude of mode(m,n)
r	radius/ distance from dipole source
ω	Angular frequency of vibration

BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION

As a critical parameter governing vibration energy dissipation in turbomachinery, the accurate characterization of aerodynamic damping is essential for the safe design of blisk (integrated bladed disk) structures. In flutter prediction, the sign of aerodynamic damping directly determines system stability, while its magnitude inversely correlates with forced response amplitudes. State-of-the-art methods for evaluating damping in forced response problems typically adopt the same modeling approach as flutter analysis, using a single blade row and one-way fluid-structure interaction simulation[1]. However, the increasing demand for higher thrust-to-weight ratios in modern engines introduces new challenges in aerodynamic damping prediction due to coupling effects inherent to blisk configurations, where

interactions between blade rows can significantly alter damping characteristics. Numerous literatures highlight the considerable influence of acoustic waves on aerodynamic damping, arising from interactions between acoustic waves and the structure around the blade. The early work by He[2] demonstrates that the aerodynamic damping due to the stator varies sinusoidally with axial spacing. More recently, CFD studies by Zhao et al[3]. on multistage compressor rotors revealed that the presence of upstream/downstream stators induces 0 nodal diameter (0ND) flutter, exposing limitations of the conventional Single-Passage Energy Method in cross-stage coupling analyses. Aerodynamic damping is also closely linked to modal shape. While most existing research focuses on the first bending and torsion modes—for example, Vahdati[4] introduced the bending-torsion ratio and emphasized the torsional component’s impact on flutter stability—far less is known about higher-order modes. Under forced vibration, these higher-order modes exhibit distinctive traits:

1. High Frequency: Modern design practices suppress low-order resonances (first flap or first torsion), shifting resonance issues to higher-order modes. Their elevated frequencies facilitate acoustic wave propagation.

2. High Circumferential Wave Number: The circumferential mode order m (ranging between $-B/2$ and $B/2$, where B is the blade count) is often large (on the order of 10) due to acoustic design requirements[5]. High m values promote acoustic cutoff in flows without circumferential mean velocity.

3. Complex Mode Shapes: Higher-order modes exhibit more complex shapes, generating acoustic waves with strong radial variations. These characteristics further complicate the aerodynamic damping characteristics of higher-order modes.

These attributes complicate the aerodynamic damping behavior of higher-order modes in multi-stage environments. Current findings regarding stage effects on high-mode damping remain contradictory:

1.5-stage compressor experiments at Technische Universität Darmstadt demonstrated minimal sensitivity of aerodynamic damping to inlet vane configurations[6] at mode 1-3. Lorenzo [7][8] also believe that the arrangement of upstream and downstream blades has no effect on the aerodynamic damping. They believe that higher-order modes of sound waves are more likely to be attenuated, so the reflection from the upstream and downstream will have little impact on the aerodynamic damping of the blades at this time. Such discrepancies suggest that aerodynamic damping depends on multiple coupled parameters—including inter-row spacing, resonance conditions, and modal properties.

To clarify the underlying mechanisms, this study employs full-annulus unsteady CFD simulations of a 1.5-stage transonic compressor. We analyze modal forces and damping

characteristics across different rotor-stator configurations and propose an acoustic dipole-based model for unsteady pressure generation, linking blade vibration distribution to acoustic mode shapes. This work also aims to reconcile why some studies report no significant effect of adjacent rows on aerodynamic damping.

METHODOLOGIES

The investigation centers on a 1.5-stage axial compressor specifically designed for aeroelastic and aerodynamic stability research, with its schematic configuration depicted in **Figure 1**, respectively. The investigated working condition is partial speed of 63% maximum corrected speed (resonance was found at this speed) with an inlet mass flow rate of 2.89 kg/s. The stage configuration comprises 15 inlet guide vanes (IGV), 28 rotor blades, and 46 stator blades (**Figure 2**). To isolate aerodynamic damping effects, the rotor is manufactured as a blisk (integrated bladed disk) from TC11 titanium alloy, exhibiting negligible structural damping with a material damping ratio of approximately 0.02%. The baseline case has a rotor-stator gap of around 25% chord length, and an IGV-rotor gap of around 30% chord length.

Figure 1 Scheme of the compressor

Figure 2 The cross section of the compressor, showing the blade number

Figure 3 The full annulus computational domain

Figure 4 The campbell diagram of the rotor blade showing the resonance point

Figure 5 Mode shape of the 4th mode with two view from suction side and pressure side

An experimental study was conducted on this compressor. The calculations of modal force and aerodynamic damping are validated by comparing the differences between experimental measurements and

simulation results at resonance points. The amplitude and damping at two resonance points were measured using a single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) fitting method, where the amplitude values represented the average across all blades near the resonance point, demonstrating good repeatability.

The full-annulus CFD simulations in this study predicted aerodynamic damping and aerodynamic excitation values of 0.045 mm and 0.0032, respectively, with maximum deviations from experimental results of 10% and 20% (see **Table 1**). The prediction error for aerodynamic damping is slightly larger, which may be attributed to the use of the SDOF fitting method. A mistuning model fitting approach could potentially yield more accurate experimental damping values. Nevertheless, the achieved accuracy supports the validity of this work.

Table 1 The experiment result of the resonance parameter

	Sweep1	Sweep2	Ave
Maximum Amplitude fitte with sDOF (mm)	0.0527	0.0473	0.0500
Resonance frequency (Hz)	31815.8	31827.5	31821.7
Damping ratio	0.0040	0.0039	0.0040

Finally, to ensure a consistent operating condition for comparing the four models, the flow conditions are validated by comparing the steady-state pressure profiles of the four models, see **Figure 6**. Although Case D exhibited a slight deviation at the leading edge, the results still demonstrate the uniformity of the analyzed operating conditions.

Figure 6 Pressure profile of different case at 85%span

MAIN RESULTS

Modal force and aerodynamic damping

Firstly, the linearity of the modal force is validated through numerical simulation. The vibrating modal force is obtained by subtracting the non-vibrating force from the vibrating force. Three vibration amplitudes (25%, 50%, and

100%) are analyzed in terms of aerodynamic forces. The analysis is conducted from both quantitative and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) perspectives, based on characteristics of linear behavior. When nonlinearity occurs, changes in amplitude and phase typically arise, and waveform distortion introduces higher-order harmonic components. As shown in **Figure 7**, the modal force exhibits a linear relationship with the vibration amplitude, although a second harmonic component appears in the spectrum at the 100% amplitude, indicating weak nonlinearity.

Therefore, under the assumption of small amplitudes, the subtraction approach mentioned above also indicates that the vibrating modal force is independent of the excitation modal force. This phenomenon demonstrates that even under transonic conditions, linear and decoupled methods can effectively capture aerodynamic damping. This is further supported by the common numerical practice in harmonic balance methods, where only the first harmonic is typically used for damping prediction. The findings reinforce the validity of treating aerodynamic damping and aerodynamic excitation separately. The above analysis also highlights the importance of avoiding excessively large amplitudes that may introduce nonlinear effects when calculating aerodynamic damping. All subsequent analyses are therefore conducted based on calculations at the 25% amplitude. However, as shown in the following analysis, even though this independence holds, the influence of upstream and downstream blade rows must still be considered when computing aerodynamic damping.

Figure 7 Modal Force of different vibrating amplitude

The modal forces, aerodynamic damping and phase different (between the modal force and vibrating velocity) for each model are presented in **Table 2**. All the models show a small variation in the modal force. The isolated rotor model (case D) exhibits the smallest amplitude, whereas the Embedded extension-out model (case B) shows the largest amplitude. The total variation across the models is of approximately 8.6%. However, the following analysis will show that this does not mean that the downstream stator has no effect on the rotor. The corresponding aerodynamic damping values shows a complex trend. The variation is around 17.7%. The isolated model has the least damping. Clearly, the difference in aerodynamic damping is not proportional to the difference in modal force, which is a

result of the phase change. As shown in the **Table 2**, the case B and isolated have the smaller phase difference. And the phase of the case A and the C are nearly identical. This means the downstream stator changes the damping by change the phase of the modal force. We should also notice that the phase different between the modal force and blade velocity is around 180 degree which means the pressure induced by the blade always do negative work on the blade.

Table 2 Modal force and Modal work

Model	Case A	Case B	Case C	Case D
Modal Force Amplitude(N)	0.1018	0.1023	0.1009	0.0928
Dev Modal Force(with baseline)	0	0.5%	-0.8%	-8.1%
Damping Ratio	3.20e-3	2.92e-3	3.29e-3	2.72e-3
Damping Dev(with baseline)	0	-8.8%	2.8%	-14.9%
Phase Difference(modal force and blade velocity, in degree)	173	168	175	155

The modal work implies the downstream vane has a strong influence on the effective aero-damping. While the result of case C shows IGV has limited impact on effective aero-damping. This result is similar to that of [6], that is, the upstream blades (guide vanes) do not have a significant impact on aerodynamic damping. Given that aerodynamic damping is related to the acoustic radiation caused by the blades, the acoustic propagation characteristics of different models will be analyzed below.

Acoustics Characteristic Isolated rotor(Case D)

Discussing the acoustic characteristics of an isolated rotor can help obtain the properties of sound waves generated by vibration, which is beneficial for analyzing the influence of upstream and downstream blades. Firstly, the sound field in the external flow channel of the blade passage is analyzed based on the traditional convective wave equation. The formula from Zhao's[9] thesis is used:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{a^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2} + M_x^2 \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} + \left(\frac{M_\theta}{r}\right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial \theta^2} + 2 \frac{M_x}{a} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x \partial t} + 2 \frac{M_\theta}{ar} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial \theta \partial t} + 2 M_x \frac{M_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x \partial \theta} \\ & = \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \end{aligned} \quad (0.1)$$

Where, M_x, M_θ are axial mach number and circumferential mach number of the mean flow, a is the acoustic speed. The equation is separable, that is, the solution can be written as:

$$p_{m,n} = f(r) \cos(k_z z + m\theta - \omega t) \quad (0.2)$$

Where f is the liner combination of Bessel function of the first kind and the second kind:

$$f_{m,n}(r) = J_m(k_{m,n}r) + \chi_{m,n}Y_m(k_{m,n}r) \quad (0.3)$$

$k_{m,n}$ $\chi_{m,n}$ are determined by the boundary condition at casing and hub (In this paper, the hard wall condition). And according to the imaginary part of k_z , the cut-on condition can be obtained:

$$(k - Ma_\theta \frac{m}{r})^2 - k_{m,n}^2(1 - Ma_x^2) \quad (0.4)$$

Here, k is the free-stream wavenumber, and m is the circumferential mode number, which is 13 in this case. n represents the radial order. All acoustic waves are propagating modes, and k_{mn} is the eigenvalue of the eigenfunction. Based on Equation (0.4), the cutoff/propagation behavior of different radial acoustic modes and their corresponding radial distributions can be determined, as shown in **Table 3**.

For the upstream region, all acoustic waves are cut off. In the downstream region, modes with $n = 0$ to 2 propagate, while those with $n \geq 3$ are cut off. This is primarily due to the high circumferential mode number studied in this work, which results in a large value for the first term in Equation (0.4).

A comparison of the different radial distributions is shown in **Figure 8**. It can be observed that as n increases, the radial variations become more complex. Note that the derivatives of all distribution functions are zero at both endpoints, which is determined by the rigid wall boundary conditions. Notably, near 80% span, the higher-order components for $n = 1$ to 3 are close to zero.

These conclusions are also reflected in the actual CFD contours as seen in **Figure 9**. For example, the acoustic field downstream of the blade at 70% and 90% span exhibits complex interference patterns, while at 80% span, the acoustic field is relatively clean and shows a traveling wave pattern. The upstream acoustic waves are confined mainly near the shock region. This indicates that the vibration mode under study excites complex radial components.

Table 3 Cut-on/off state of different radial mode, “+” is cut-on, “-”is cut off

m=13	Inlet	Outlet
0	-	+
1	-	+
2	-	+
3	-	-

Figure 8 Radial distribution of different radial mode

Figure 9 Acoustic field of Case D rotor at 70%-80%-90%span

Furthermore, the acoustic field can be written in the form of $f = \sum_n a_{m,n} f_{m,n}$. By utilizing the orthogonal relationship of the radial function:

$$\int_{hub}^{shroud} f_{m,n} \cdot f_{m,n'} r dr = \delta(n, n') \quad (0.5)$$

where $\delta(n, n')$ is the delta symbol, if $n=n'$, $\delta(n, n')=1$ otherwise $\delta(n, n')=0$. The components of different radial modes in the flow field can be determined. As shown in the **Figure 10**, the components for $n = 0-3$ are presented. It can be clearly seen that the intensities of the first three radial orders are relatively large. The intensities of the fourth order and above are close to 0 due to acoustic cutoff.

Figure 10 Amplitude of acoustic mode at rotor exit, Case D

Given the relatively large vibration displacement near the higher span section of the blade, the blade-to-blade dynamic pressure characteristics at the 85% span are examined. It is observed that the unsteady pressure on the pressure surface and suction surface exhibited distinctly different behaviors.

On the pressure surface, significant dynamic pressure fluctuations are identified, with high amplitudes localized near the trailing edges—regions corresponding to larger blade vibration displacements. Moreover, the pressure gradient in the vicinity of the blade passage surface is perpendicular to the pressure surface (see **Figure 11**). This suggests a certain directivity in the acoustic waves along the blade surface. Beyond 0.3 chord length, however, this high-amplitude region diminished. This behavior can be analyzed using the Ffowcs Williams–Hawkings (FW-H) equation[10]. According to the FW-H equation, the pressure field generated by vibration is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{c^2 \partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i^2} \right) p' = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\rho(u_i - v_i)] \delta(g) \frac{\partial g}{\partial x_i} \\ - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} [p \delta_{ij} - \rho u_i (u_j - v_j)] \delta(g) \frac{\partial g}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial T_{ij}}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \end{aligned} \quad (0.6)$$

In the equation, v_i represents the velocity of the moving solid surface, and u_i denotes the local flow velocity, g is a function of space and time and $g=0$ on the moving surface. Since the FW-H equation assumes a non-penetrable condition on the moving surface, u_i can be regarded as the velocity of the potential flow outside the boundary layer. The right-hand side of Equation (0.6) includes terms related to the vibrational velocity: the first term represents the monopole source, the second term corresponds to the dipole source, and the final term signifies the quadrupole source.

As can be seen from the above equation, the sound sources induced by vibration are proportional to the

vibrational velocity. Furthermore, the pressure wave sources generated by blade vibration are predominantly in the form of dipole sources (the second term in the equation, denoted as $F(t)$), which explains the directivity characteristic observed in the contour plots. The acoustic field of a single dipole source can be expressed by the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} p'(r, \theta, t) = -\cos \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{F(t - r/a)}{4\pi r} \right] \\ = -\frac{\cos \theta}{4\pi} \left[\frac{1}{ar} \frac{\partial F}{\partial t} + \frac{F}{r^2} \right] \Bigg|_{t_r = t - r/c_0} \end{aligned} \quad (0.7)$$

θ is the angle between receiver and the dipole axis. From(0.7), there are two term controlling the acoustic amplitude one with the order of $o\left(\frac{1}{r}\right)$, which is decaying slowly with distance, and can be called as far field component. Another term, $o\left(\frac{1}{r^2}\right)$, decay rapidly and is called the near field component. Mathematically, since the near-field component is $o\left(\frac{1}{r^2}\right)$, the pressure inside the blade channel is higher than the far-field component. From the CFD scale, the position where the near-field component dominates is such that the near-field component is approximately 10 times that of the far-field. A critical size can be defined:

$$l_c = \frac{a}{\omega} \quad (0.8)$$

When the distance is smaller than l_c , the near field component is dominant. For the 85% span section of this compressor, the characteristic scale mentioned above is approximately 0.2 chord length, which is on the same order of magnitude as the gap between the rotor and stator in Case A. As a result, the stator lies within the near-field region of the dipole source. In this scenario—similar to the behavior observed under cut-off conditions in the downstream region—the interaction is dominated by near-field effects rather than the reflection of propagating far-field acoustic waves.

Therefore, it can be expected that when the gap is within the dipole near-field range, the influence of the upstream and downstream blade rows will be independent of whether far-field acoustic propagation occurs.

Figure 11 The source of the unsteady pressure

The above analysis provides an insight that the radial distribution of vibration modes is related to that of acoustic modes. To explore this relationship, the radial distribution of the vibration displacement of the blade is extracted, and the velocity index is defined as:

$$v_{index}(r) = \oint v_z(r, s) ds \quad (0.9)$$

The integral is conducted at a certain span. The final result is expanded using the acoustic radial distribution(0.5), **Figure 12** shows the acoustic radial mode and the expand of velocity index.

Figure 12 The relationship between the pressure coefficients (black dot) of different radial modes and the velocity indices component (red dot)

As shown in the **Figure 12**, the vibration velocity distribution along the radial direction exhibits a distinct peak at $n = 1$. Qualitatively, the distribution of vibration velocity resembles that of the acoustic mode. This suggests a strong correlation between the radial distribution of the vibration mode and the radial distribution of the acoustic mode.

To validate this relationship, a study is also conducted on a first-order flat-wise mode. The same extraction and correlation procedures for acoustic and velocity field coefficients, as described above, are applied. Additionally, the following pressure response coefficient is defined:

$$A_{m,n} = a_{m,n}^{acoustics} / a_{m,n}^{vibration} \quad (0.10)$$

That is, the acoustic amplitude divided by the vibration velocity amplitude. **Figure 13** shows the response coefficients of different radial acoustic modes corresponding to different vibration modes. A comparison of the coefficients from the two modes reveals that, although there are certain differences in specific amplitudes, the trends across different radial modes are quite consistent. The mode at $n = 1$ exhibits the most significant response to vibration, and the coefficients differ considerably between the two vibration modes. In contrast, the response of other-order modes is relatively weak.

The discrepancy in coefficients between the two modes may be attributed to an inappropriate velocity index. Further investigation will be conducted to determine a suitable velocity exponent to establish the relationship between acoustic modal intensity and excitation strength.

Figure 13 Pressure response coefficient of different vibrating mode

As shown in **Figure 11**, The unsteady pressure on the suction surface is relatively small and exhibits clear characteristics of shock oscillation. Although the upstream acoustic field is cut off, the influence of the shock waves still extends approximately two chord lengths downstream.

From the pressure gradient contours, it can be observed that two distinct shock waves are present on the suction surface: The first shock, located near the leading edge at the tip, is relatively strong. The second shock is a detached shock with weaker intensity.

The unsteady aerodynamic forces induced by these shocks are distributed in multiple segments along the blade surface, resulting in an alternating pattern of high-pressure, low-pressure, and high-pressure regions in the flow field. Both shock waves excite unsteady pressure fluctuations that propagate upstream. Unlike the downstream acoustic behavior, these upstream propagating disturbances travel almost parallel to the blade surface, which is a notable difference compared to the pressure-side acoustic waves.

This phenomenon also demonstrates strong directivity. From an aerodynamic perspective, the shock wave can be treated as a wall with varying load, a concept also noted in the work of Farrassat et al[11]. However, the spatial extent of the shock influence is larger than that of a pure wall-induced dipole, reaching approximately chord-length scale. Even though the acoustic field is in a cut-off state, the shock waves may still interact with upstream blade rows.

Embedded rotor(Case A-C): Downstream of the rotor blade

The unsteady pressure field of different case at 85% are shown in **Figure 14**. Examining the blade-to-blade dynamic pressure characteristics at the 85% span section reveals that both the pressure and suction surfaces in Case A exhibit unsteady pressure features similar to those in Case D. On the pressure side, significant dynamic pressure fluctuations are observed with regions of high amplitude. However, in terms of spatial distribution, the high-pressure zone in Case A extends across the entire chord, whereas in Case D it is primarily concentrated near the trailing edge. Meanwhile, Case C, which shares the same rotor-stator gap as Case A, demonstrates characteristics largely identical to those of Case A. In contrast, the results of Case B show a high-pressure distribution similar to that of Case D. This region extends axially downstream by approximately 0.3 times the rotor chord length—smaller than that in Case D—and originates near the projection of the adjacent blade and the current blade, without further upstream propagation. This difference is clearly attributed to the influence of the downstream stator.

From the radial distribution of the rotor-stator gap (**Figure 15**), it is evident that the $n = 1$ component is significantly stronger in Case B and Case D. This appears contradictory to the differences in modal force. However, the contour plots show that the high-pressure regions in Cases B and D are shifted toward the outlet direction, altering the pressure distribution on the blade surface and resulting in a relatively low modal force. Additionally, in Case B, the dynamic pressure distribution on the pressure surface exhibits an additional nodal line located near the leading

edge (**Figure 16**). As a result, the influence of the downstream stator penetrates across the entire blade passage. The pressure distribution on blade suction side is also shown in **Figure 17**, The similarity of Case A and Case C is evidence, showing the negative-positive-negative variation along the tip chord, and the rapid variation at around 70%span which are different with Case D and Case B. This indicates the stator-row has the influence on both pressure side and suction side of the rotor blade.

Figure 14 Unsteady Pressure field at 85%span of different case

Figure 15 Acoustic mode in the rotor-stator gap, also showing the isolated rotor exit result

Figure 16 Pressure distribution on the pressure side

Figure 17 Pressure distribution on the suction side

The acoustic component at stator exit is shown in **Figure 18**. For the different cases, the dominant radial wavenumbers are $n = 0, 1,$ and 2 . A certain amplitude of the $n = 3$ component also persists after passing through the stator. The

components in Cases A–C are highly similar, indicating that the upstream guide vanes have no significant influence on the downstream acoustic field.

However, the amplitude of the $n = 1$ and $n = 2$ components in Case B is significantly reduced, suggesting that the reflected acoustic waves weaken the sound field at this location. Meanwhile, the $n = 0$ component in Case B remains largely unchanged. This observation also explains why the downstream acoustic waves in Case B exhibit a cleaner traveling wave mode.

The above results further indicate that the transmission coefficient of the radial acoustic modes through the stator depends on both the radial mode order and the rotor-stator gap, as detailed in the **Table 4** below. The transmission coefficient for the $n = 0$ mode is relatively high, around 0.9. The transmission coefficient for $n = 1$ also reflects the influence of the downstream rotor in Case B. It is noteworthy that for higher-order acoustic modes, transmission coefficients exceeding 1 are observed.

Figure 18 Acoustic mode at stator exit

Table 4 The transmission coefficient through the stator

n	Case A	Case B	Case C
0	0.89	0.77	0.90
1	0.67	0.18	0.66
2	1.39	0.46	1.35
3	1.06	1.68	0.92

The above analyses all focus on the directly aliased 13ND mode. By examining the circumferential pressure distribution in the rotor-stator gap (**Figure 19**), it is evident that acoustic waves at 33ND are also present in the gap. These result from the Tyler-Sofrin interaction between the 13ND mode and the downstream row of 46 blades. Although this interference occurs, the frequency of the resulting acoustic mode in the relative frame differs from the blade vibration frequency. Therefore, it does not contribute to the aerodynamic damping.

Figure 19 Circumferential wave number in the rotor-stator gap

Embedded rotor (Case A-C): Upstream of the rotor blade

As shown in **Figure 20**, significant pressure fluctuations remain present upstream and interact with the inlet guide vanes (IGVs), reflecting and altering their direction of propagation. This results in strong interference patterns within the blade passage. Ultimately, these fluctuations gradually dissipate in the far upstream region due to numerical damping in the mesh.

All reflected waves propagate upstream and have minimal impact on the downstream domain. The pressure waves caused by IGV reflection also form interference patterns upstream. Analysis of the radial distribution near the rotor leading edge shows little difference in amplitude across different cases and modes, further supporting the absence of significant acoustic reflection.

Figure 21 shows the acoustic component in the gap between the IGV and rotor blade. Compared to the rotor outlet, the amplitudes of acoustic modes $n = 0$ to 4 are higher at the inlet, which is also attributed to shock-related effects.

Given that the test rig in [6] is also a transonic/supersonic compressor with similar flow characteristics, the observed lack of IGV influence on aerodynamic damping in the TUDA open-test case may be due to the same mechanism. The strength of the shock is affected by the IGVs: in the baseline configuration, the fluctuations before and after the shock are more intense, and a distinct reflected chordwise direction is evident. It should be noted, however, that if the IGV installation angle is increased such that the reflected shock becomes parallel to the shock surface, secondary motion of the shock surface can be induced. This would further alter the blade surface pressure in the shock region and modify the aerodynamic damping.

Figure 20 The reflection of shock wave from IGV

The acoustic modes at the rotor inlet are also extracted. The composition of the radial acoustic modes is more complex, with modes from order 0 to 4 present, which is clearly attributed to shock effects. Moreover, after extending the inlet section, the upstream acoustic waves are significantly reduced. This reduction occurs because the shock moves farther away from the guide vanes, greatly diminishing the interaction between the shock-induced dipole and the blades.

However, the amplitude of the $n = 2$ mode in Case B is significantly lower than in Cases A and C, indicating that the acoustic waves reflected by the downstream stator penetrate through the rotor.

Figure 21 Acoustic mode in the IGV-rotor gap, also showing the isolated rotor inlet result

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Accurate prediction of aerodynamic damping is crucial for ensuring the safe design of blisk structures, particularly considering its significant influence on the flutter stability and forced response amplitudes. This study investigates the effects of blade row interaction on aerodynamic damping using fully three-dimensional unsteady CFD simulations for a transonic compressor configuration. The main conclusions are drawn as follows:

1. The results demonstrate that the downstream-propagating wave induced by blade vibration is cut-on, while the upstream-propagating wave is cut-off but the shock wave still interacts with the IGV blade. By comparing the modal forces across the different numerical models it is found that the modal force amplitude is nearly independent with the change stage environment. While aero-damping varies significantly due to the change of phase of modal force. These findings highlight the significant impact of adjacent blade rows and inter-row spacing on the aerodynamic damping.

2. In the vibration of transonic compressor blades, the mechanisms of aerodynamic disturbance generation differ between the pressure surface and the suction surface. On the

pressure surface, the vibration directly alters the unsteady blade loading, forming a dipole source aligned with the blade vibration velocity. On the suction surface, the vibration induces shock motion, which dominates acoustic wave generation. The shock wave itself can be regarded as a dipole source oriented normal to the shock surface. The interaction between these dipole sources and the upstream/downstream blade rows governs the unsteady pressure field, leading to changes in aerodynamic damping. At the inlet, due to the stagger angle of the guide vanes, no significant reflected acoustic waves are observed; thus, no notable effect on damping is identified.

3. By correlating the radial distribution of blade vibration velocity with the eigenfunctions of the acoustic modes, a quantitative relationship is identified between the coefficients of the radial decomposition of vibration velocity and those of the acoustic modes. This proportional relationship appears to be largely independent of the blade mode, offering a new perspective for modeling acoustic fields generated by vibration.

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